

The information about Dogme language teaching

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Abstract: This article discusses the Dogme method, one of the new methods of English. The author of this method is also given detailed information about its application. There is also information about the techniques and advantages of using this method.

Key words: Dogme method, ELT, English Language Teaching, Teaching Unplugged, pops up, the right conditions, topic for class.

Dogme language teaching is considered to be both a methodology and a movement.⁶ The Dogme method first became known in 2000 from an article by methodologist Scott Thornbury "A Dogme for ELT"⁷, where he criticized the excessive use of additional materials during foreign language teaching, which, in his opinion, complicates and burdens the learning process. Scott Thornbury's supporter and supporter is Luke Meddings. He shares the point of view of Scott Thornbury that the modern lesson is too overloaded with textbooks, manuals, printouts, technologies. On the one hand, their use helps the teacher to diversify the lesson, and on the other hand, it does not make it possible to deviate from the curriculum, go beyond a particular topic of the lesson, suppressing the initiative coming directly from the students. As an alternative, Scott Thornbury and Luke Meddings suggest abandoning all materials, moving to a live

⁶. Luke, Meddings (2004-03-26). "Throw away your textbooks". The Guardian. Retrieved 2009-06-22.

⁷. Thornbury, Scott (February–March 2000). "A Dogma for EFL" (153). IATEFL Issues: 2. Retrieved 2009-06-23.

conversation between the teacher and students, based on real life experience, using the grammar and vocabulary that students own at this stage of learning. This point of view is described in the book “Teaching Unplugged: Dogme in English Language Teaching” by Scott Thornbury and Luke Meddings, in which the authors identify three main “commandments” of the Dogme method:

- learning based on communication;
- minimal use of additional educational materials and technologies;
- use of "live" spontaneous language.⁸

The meaning of the title of the book “Teaching Unplugged: Dogme in English Language Teaching”, taking into account the meaning of the word “unplug”, can be interpreted as “learning without a textbook”.

Teachers often use Dogme style, which is a variation of the communicative approach to language teaching. It allows you to move away from textbooks and lesson plans as much as possible and focus on communication between the student and the teacher.

“Conversation occupies almost the main place in teaching the language according to the Dogme method in the sense that “the direction of the lesson is determined by what occurs in the conversation between the teacher and students”⁹

In this approach, the class as such does not exist - there are current topics and lively communication that encourages students to use certain vocabulary and grammar.

As you understand, in this case, the lesson is unpredictable, and the learning material usually “pops up” in the process. The role of the teacher here is to optimize the language learning process.

⁸. Thornbury S., Meddings L. Teaching Unplugged: Dogme in English Language Teaching. – DELTA Publishing, 2009. – 104 p.

⁹. Джени Райт, Кристина Ребуфет-Бродус “Experimental Practice in ELT: Walk on the wild side”, 2013, с.117

The training of adult listeners, in comparison with schoolchildren, has its own characteristics, due to the peculiarities of their motivational sphere, which is a complex internal process due to the subjective-personal interest of a person in a certain action. Their motivation is characterized by such forms as intention, goal, aspiration, as well as the type of need, degree of relevance, scale, content of the activities being implemented, etc. ¹⁰

The name and basic principle for the new approach to teaching a foreign language was the avant-garde cinematic movement "Dogma 95", one of the ideologists of which was the famous Danish film director and screenwriter Lars von Trier. The principles of the movement are described in the "Dogme 95 manifesto", some of the provisions of which formed the basis of the new Dogme method:

- creation of favorable conditions ("the right conditions"), contributing to the creation of a favorable situation conducive to communication;
- organization of the communication process ("managing conversation"), which means the interaction of the teacher and students, their live spontaneous communication on topics that concern all participants in the communication, where the teacher acts not only as the organizer of the conversation, but also as its direct active participant;
- selection of a stimulus for the exchange of information ("selecting stimulus to share") requires the proactivity of the teacher, as an important component of successful communication based on the use of the current situation as a topic of conversation;
- focusing on the form ("focusing on form") or the study of the language that occurs directly in the course of the conversation
- return to the studied material ("learning from lesson to lesson") and its consolidation with the help of various techniques and exercises.

¹⁰ . Родионова И.В., Титова О.А. Специфика мотивационной основы обучения иностранному языку взрослых // Актуальные проблемы германистики, романистики и русистики. – 2016. – Т. 2. – С. 93-98.

Unlike the communicative approach, which involves the use of the language being studied, both in assignments and for communication with the teacher and within the group, in the Dogme method, live communication between the teacher and the student comes to the fore. Therefore, many modern methodologists call for using it together with a communicative approach for a more productive approach to practice and communication.¹¹

In general terms, the Dogme method of teaching is based on communication, not tied to any teaching aids, using language as a means to achieve certain results. It's more than just a method. This is a different level of teaching, focused on unlocking the potential of students through communication, interaction between both students and the teacher, the active use of personal experience, the use of personal information and situational presentation of the language.

The Dogme method lesson is based on three main principles:

- conversation oriented;
- a small amount of materials;
- focuses on new language units that arise during the lesson.

To date, the Dogme method has not yet become widespread in Russia, only some of the principles of this method have been reflected in our reality, providing the most productive implementation of the communicative approach. In the style of Dogme there is lightness, freedom, spontaneity, jazz, and at the same time there is discipline and structure, but not intrusive. However, Dogme goes beyond this point of view, as the conversation must be about “the people who are in the classroom” in order to be truly meaningful to students.

It can be concluded that the application of this method or some of its principles within the framework of a communicative methodology in the course of teaching a

¹¹. Батракова Е.Б. Dogme Teaching в обучении иностранному языку [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <http://www.rusnauka.com>. – Заглавие с экрана. (дата обращения: 20.12.2016).

foreign language, starting from school and continuing to study at universities, can contribute to the most effective interaction between students and the teacher, strengthening students' confidence in their abilities when studying foreign language, overcoming the language barrier and, as a result, reaching a new modern level of foreign language proficiency, since free and relaxed speech allows you to resolve many domestic and professional disputes and get out of them with dignity. It is obvious that “here much has something in common with the “commandments” of other transformative pedagogies, such as humanistic, critical, opportunity pedagogy, frontier pedagogy, and the like. Indeed, one of the pleasures of dogmatic discussion has been to point out these connections. In short, there is nothing very original in Dogme,” writes Scott Thornbury. When Thornbury said that "there is nothing very original in Dogme", he meant that many teachers who adhere to the principles of Dogme, in fact, only use some of the aspects of the communicative approach, humanistic and critical pedagogy, as well as other "materials -light" approaches when teaching English. Dogme aims to bring the student back to the center of the language learning process. Previous communicative language teaching methods have relied on the teacher's or curricula's decision regarding lesson content, as well as traditional classroom table and chair arrangements and limited lesson plans. Proponents of the Dogme method, on the other hand, generally prefer the arrangement of the chairs of the teacher and students in a circle (which gives students the opportunity to choose a language focus or topic for class) and the use of very few resources - many opt for whiteboard markers, a pen and some paper.

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